

Photonic-Assisted Analog-to-Digital Conversion based on a Dispersion-Diversity Multicore Fiber

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Abstract—Multigigabit-per-second photonic-assisted time-interleaved analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) built upon a dispersion-diversity multicore fiber (MCF) is proposed and experimentally demonstrated for the first time to our knowledge. Tunable true-time delay line operation for the analog signal replicas is provided by the different cores of a heterogeneous MCF, which feature different radial dimensions and GeO₂ dopant concentrations. Continuous real-time ADC tunability with the optical wavelength is experimentally demonstrated by time interleaving 5 digitized channels achieving equivalent sampling rates of 25, 50 and 125 GS/s for optical wavelengths of 1538, 1534 and 1531.6 nm, respectively. These values are beyond the 10.25-GS/s sampling rates offered by commercial electronic ADCs. One of the advantages of using a MCF for the parallel channels relies on the fact that all the cavities are subject to similar environmental conditions. The introduction of space and dispersion diversities provided by MCFs in photonic-assisted ADCs brings benefits in terms of size, weight, and power consumption reduction along with system flexibility and stability improvement. This is of particular relevance in those application scenarios where an optical fiber link is required to distribute the signal, such as fiber distributed sensing networks, as well as access networks for radar systems or next-generation wireless communications.

Index Terms—Analog-to-digital converters, time-interleaving, chromatic dispersion, multicore fibers, space-division multiplexing.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE exploitation of photonic technologies to enable analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) has proven essential to overcome the bottleneck of their electronic counterparts, mainly in terms of bandwidth and timing jitter, [1-3]. This benefit is of particular interest in next-generation information paradigms such as high-capacity optical networks, radar and electronic warfare, remote sensing, imaging, as well as advanced test instrumentation, which demand ADCs with ever-increasing sampling rates and bandwidth along with adequate accuracy, [4-8].

Over the past few decades, a rich variety of photonics techniques for wideband ADCs have been developed. Starting from optically clocked configurations applying

time interleaving of a set of optical samples [9]; wavelength division sampling where the signal is modulated over chirped broadband pulses and wavelength demultiplexed [10]; to photonic time stretching schemes where the electrical signal is compressed by stretching the waveform in time before being digitized for instance, by propagating the signal through a dispersive fiber medium, [11]. Furthermore, high-speed photonic sampling ADC using both time and wavelength interleaving in an ultra-short optical pulse train has been demonstrated recently, [12], but this approach requires the use of multiple lasers besides the WDM multiplexing devices. Data recovery via fully convolutional neural networks has also been applied to photonic ADC lately [13].

Among the different classes in which photonic ADCs can be divided, photonic-assisted ADCs, where electronics benefit from the inherent advantages of photonics to enhance some of its limiting properties while the sampling and quantization processes are made by electronic ADCs, [1], are particularly interesting due to their direct compatibility with current optical communications networks bringing, as a consequence, a cost-effective solution. Up to date, the sampling rate of commercial electronic ADCs is limited to 10.25 GS/s, [14]. The main idea behind photonic-assisted ADC architectures relies on the incorporation of a set of N parallel electronic ADCs to process, at the same time, N different replicas of the incoming signal to increase the effective sampling rate of the overall ADC beyond the limits of a single electronic ADC while allowing real-time operation.

Fig. 1. Representative application scenarios for photonic-assisted analog-to-digital conversion based on a dispersion-diversity multicore fiber link, including fiber distributed sensing networks, as well as access networks for radar systems or next-generation wireless communications.

We have previously proposed the exploitation of dispersion-diversity multicore fibers (MCF) [15] to provide parallel optical and microwave signal processing while the signal is being distributed with increased compactness and reduced power consumption, along with improved performance versatility and flexibility [16-22]. The so-called dispersion-diversity MCF involves tailoring “à la carte” the chromatic dispersion of each individual fiber core. Combining this property with the space and optical wavelength degrees of freedom in a single fiber link opens the way to a comprehensive range of dispersion-managed digital and analogue signal processing applications. Representative application scenarios include interference-controlled signal distribution in Multiple-Input Multiple-Output configurations, parallel chromatic dispersion compensation, time differentiation and integration, Fourier transformation, self-imaging phenomena (Talbot effects) to provide pulse repetition rate multiplication, waveform generation and shaping, optical beamforming for phased-array antennas, radiofrequency signal filters, instantaneous radiofrequency measurement and multicavity optoelectronic oscillation, among others [17].

Parallel signal management in most of the above-mentioned areas involves recombination of a given set of signal replicas with different time group delays, what can be provided in a continuously tunable way by the dispersion-diversity MCF. We propose in this work to apply the same principle to enable multigigabit-per-second photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC, where the sampling rate can be increased by a factor given by the number of fiber cores N . The rationale behind this approach lies in the application of our tunable MCF-based true-time delay line (TTDL) to provide and control the required multiple time-delay replicas of the analog signal. After synchronous low-rate sampling by electronic commercial ADCs, the replicas are properly recombined to recover the final high-rate digitized signal. Among other key features, this architecture allows for real-time sampling rate tunability and remote system reconfigurability, providing the system with higher degrees of flexibility and versatility, essential demands of next-generation optical and fiber wireless communication paradigms. Figure 1 illustrates some representative application scenarios in which a dispersion-diversity

Fig. 2. Illustration of the operation principle for the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC architecture based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF.

MCF-enabled ADC could bring unprecedented features in terms of performance and compactness.

In this paper, we propose and experimentally demonstrate, for the first time, photonic analog-to-digital conversion based on a dispersion-diversity MCF. First, we develop the principle of operation based on the tunable MCF-based TTDL and the application of time interleaving. Then, we describe the main characteristics of the fabricated ad hoc heterogeneous MCF link. Continuous real-time ADC tunability with the optical wavelength is experimentally demonstrated by time interleaving 5 signal replicas achieving equivalent sampling rates up to 125 GS/s. Finally, we provide further discussion about the performance limits of the proposed architecture.

II. TIME-INTERLEAVED DISPERSION-DIVERSITY-MCF CONCEPT

Figure 2 represents the operation principle of the proposed time-interleaved photonic-assisted ADC architecture. As every time-interleaved ADC system, the fundamental idea consists of sampling a given input analog signal by means of a set of N parallel digitizers of lower sampling rate, and the subsequent application of digital interleaving as to increase the overall system sampling rate by a factor of N . In our approach, the key building block is a N -core dispersion-engineered heterogeneous MCF that has been designed to behave as a tunable sampled TTDL. As Fig. 2 shows, the input analog signal is split and injected into the N cores of the MCF to obtain, at the fiber output, N time-delayed replicas of the input signal. The replicas are then sampled by a set of N parallel electronic ADCs sequentially clocked at a sampling rate f_s . Finally, they are recombined to properly perform the digital interleaving that leads to a digitized signal with an equivalent sampling rate $f_{s,eq} = N \cdot f_s$.

The differential group delay (DGD) between adjacent replicas $\Delta\tau$, is synthesized by the MCF itself. The MCF is dispersion-engineered to provide a common $\Delta\tau$ between each pair of adjacent cores, which can also be tuned with the optical wavelength as

$$\Delta\tau(\lambda) = \Delta D \cdot (\lambda - \lambda_0), \quad (1)$$

being λ_0 the anchor wavelength where all the cores experience an identical group delay, $\tau_n(\lambda_0) = \tau_0$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, and $\Delta D = D_n - D_{n-1}$, $n = 2, 3, \dots, N$, the incremental chromatic dispersion between adjacent cores at λ_0 , [16, 17].

For the photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC to increase the sampling rate of the parallel electronic ADCs, f_s , by a factor N , the DGD between cores must satisfy the relation

$$T_s = 1/f_s = N \cdot \Delta\tau, \quad (2)$$

being T_s the sampling time of the electronic ADCs. Then, the equivalent sampling rate for the photonic-assisted

Fig. 3. Photograph of the cross-section area of the fabricated heterogeneous MCF.

TABLE I
CORE REFRACTIVE INDEX DESIGN PARAMETERS. DESIGNED AND MEASURED CHROMATIC DISPERSIONS AT $\lambda_0 = 1530$ nm.

Core n	Designed					Measured
	a_1 (μm)	Δ_1 (%)	a_2/a_1	w/a_1	D (ps/km/nm)	D_{CSE} (ps/km/nm)
1	3.3	0.335	1.758	0.970	14.30	13.85
2	3.2	0.300	0.750	1.281	15.30	14.95
3	3.5	0.315	1.286	1.143	16.30	16.35
4	3.7	0.301	1.000	0.973	17.30	17.30
5	4.8	0.293	1.208	0.625	18.30	18.25
6	5.0	0.287	0.920	1.200	19.30	19.30
7	5.3	0.279	0.623	1.132	20.30	20.30

time-interleaved ADC results

$$f_{s,eq} = N \cdot f_s = 1/\Delta\tau, \quad (3)$$

that is, the equivalent sampling time equals the DGD between cores, $T_{s,eq} = \Delta\tau$. Since $\Delta\tau$ can be tuned with the operation wavelength of the optical source, we see from (3) that the equivalent sampling rate can be tuned adaptively depending on the operation optical wavelength. Although the electronic ADCs have fixed sampling rate, parallel configurations can be implemented, simultaneously while the signals are being distributed through a single dispersion-engineered heterogeneous MCF link. For instance, having a matrix of $M \times N$ electronic ADCs with sampling rates $f_{s,m}$ would allow the implementation of M parallel time-interleaved ADCs operating at different optical wavelengths with the condition that the ADCs' sampling time $T_{s,m}$ of each row m satisfies (2).

From Fig. 2, we can easily follow that the proposed architecture supports real time operation. Given an input real-time analog signal, we see that either the optical replication or the parallel sampling is performed in continuous time. For the digital interleaving step, an

Fig. 4. a) Measured spectral DGD with respect to core 7 ($\tau_7 - \tau_n$), and b) mean value of the measured DGD between adjacent cores ($\Delta\tau$) for cores 3 to 7 (red-filled squares), along with the maximum deviation (error bars) and the trend line for the mean $\Delta\tau$ (black line).

inverse DGD stage can be applied to undo the different DGD applied to each replica and thus recover the sampling of the original signal for the digitized signal, which is compatible with continuous time operation.

III. DISPERSION-DIVERSITY MULTICORE FIBER

We have developed a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF for tunable TTDL operation. It comprises seven distinct trench-assisted cores drawn from seven different preforms and placed in a hexagonal disposition. The refractive index profile of each core was tailored independently to satisfy a common group delay at the anchor wavelength $\lambda_0 = 1530$ nm with linearly incremental chromatic dispersion values, D_n , ranging from 14.3 to 20.3 ps/km/nm, respectively for cores 1 up to 7, with an incremental chromatic dispersion $\Delta D = 1$ ps/km/nm, [17]. Table 1 gathers the design parameters of each core refractive index profile along with the measured chromatic dispersions. Each core has different radial dimensions and GeO_2 dopant concentrations. The core

radii a_1 range from 3.2 up to 5.3 μm , with core-to-cladding relative index differences, Δ_1 , ranging from 0.279% up to 3.335%. Each core layer is followed by a pure silica inner cladding of variable width a_2 and a 1%-F-doped trench layer of variable width w . The core arrangement inside the cladding was set to minimize intercore crosstalk by ensuring adjacent cores have the maximum effective refractive index difference. From that, we find the critical bending radius for this fiber is 8.55 cm.

Figure 3 shows a photograph of the cross-section of the fabricated MCF, where we appreciate the different radial dimensions of each core. A total length of 5.038 km was drawn by the company YOFC. The cladding diameter is 147.5 μm and the average core pitch is 41 μm . Accounting for both the fiber link and the fan-in/fan-out devices, the measured total insertion losses range from 4.6 to 7.7 dB, while the measured inter-core crosstalk is below -26.9 dB at 1560 nm in the worst-case (cores 1 and 2). A complete experimental characterization of this MCF, including among others crosstalk time variation and spectra, influence of temperature on the fiber skew, and spectral chromatic dispersion behavior, can be found in [17].

Table 1 compares the designed and the measured chromatic dispersion for each core. We measured the chromatic dispersion by evaluating the carrier suppression effect on the radiofrequency response of the 5-km fiber link. We observe a good agreement between design and fabrication for cores 3 to 7, which deliver a differential chromatic dispersion ΔD of 1 ps/km/nm. In contrast, cores 1 and 2 present a deviation in the chromatic dispersion. This is likely caused by fabrication inaccuracies as small cores are more sensitive to radial variations.

Next, we evaluated the capability of this fiber to provide continuous tunable TTDL operation. We measured the DGD at different optical wavelengths from 1530 to 1560 nm using an optical interferometric technique [23]. Figure 4(a) depicts the measured DGDs as a function of the optical wavelength with respect to core 7. Circle markers represent the measured values and solid lines the trend with the optical wavelength. In line with the measured dispersion values, we appreciate that cores 3 to 7 present a linearly incremental delay with the optical wavelength without significant deviation and non-linearities within a 30-nm range. Figure 4(b) illustrates the measured spectral space-diversity differential group delay $\Delta\tau$ for cores 3 to 7, where red-filled squares represent the mean measured differential group delays, error bars show their maximum deviation, and the black solid line represents the trend line for the mean values.

Therefore, in the space-diversity domain (i.e., signal samples are provided by different cores for a given input optical wavelength), we achieved up to 5-sample tunable TDDL operation with a tunable differential delay from 0 up to 150 ps when the optical wavelength is varied from 1530 to 1560 nm. Even so, in the wavelength-diversity domain (i.e., signal samples are provided by different input optical wavelengths within a given core), we must note that all cores can be employed as independent tunable TDDLs. In addition, cores 1 and 2 could be exploited to transmit independent data channels, or included as part of the space-diversity TDDL for other applications in which constant time delays are not necessary, [24].

IV. PHOTONIC ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERSION EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The unique properties of the fabricated dispersion-diversity MCF grant the implementation of distributed high-speed ADC by using the proposed optical time-interleaving technique. One of the main advantages of this approach relies on the continuous time delay tunability of the implemented TDDL, which allows adaptive sampling rates by simply tuning the optical wavelength, adding a new degree of system flexibility. Figure 5 depicts the experimental setup for the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC. As the driving RF signal, we use a periodic triangular waveform with a period of 800 ps generated by an arbitrary waveform generator. The RF signal is modulated onto the optical carrier coming from a tunable laser via an intensity modulator. The modulated signal is then amplified and injected into cores 3 to 7 of the heterogeneous MCF, which, depending on the operation optical wavelength of the tunable laser, apply a particular differential group delay to the propagated signals. At the optical wavelength

$\lambda = 1530$ nm (anchor wavelength), the time delay experienced in each of the MCF cores is identical, in accordance with Fig. 4. As the operation wavelength of the optical source increases, the differential time delay between signal samples increases linearly with the optical wavelength. This property is accomplished thanks to the chromatic dispersion diversity provided by the fabricated MCF. At the fiber output, the amplitude of each signal is adjusted by means of a variable optical attenuator (VOA). The samples are then photodetected and amplified independently and visualized in a digital phosphor oscilloscope (DPO). The measured waveforms are digitally sampled and time-interleaved to obtain the equivalent sampling rate of the photonic-assisted ADC.

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the experimental setup for the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF. Upper graphs represent the measured RF input signal (left) and the measured received signals from cores 3 up to 7 in the DPO when the laser operates at the optical wavelength of 1530 nm. PC: polarization controller; AWG: Arbitrary waveform generator; EOM: electro-optic modulator; EDFA: Erbium doped fiber amplifier; MCF: Multicore fiber; VOA: Variable optical attenuator; PD: Photodetector; RF: radiofrequency; DPO: Digital phosphor oscilloscope.

Figure 6 illustrates the implemented ADC process for different optical wavelengths. Figures 6(a)-(c) show the measured waveforms in the DPO for each MCF core at $\lambda = 1531.6, 1534$ and 1538 nm, respectively. We see how the differential time delay between samples increases as the optical wavelength breaks away from the anchor wavelength of 1530 nm. In particular, the differential time delay between adjacent samples results in $\Delta\tau = 8, 20$ and 40 ps, respectively for $\lambda = 1531.6, 1534$ and 1538 nm, as expected from Fig. 4(b). According to (2), the required sampling rates for the parallel electronic ADCs are $25, 10$ and 5 GS/s, respectively for $\lambda = 1531.6, 1534$ and 1538 nm. Figures 6(d)-(f) represent the temporal digital sampling applied to each waveform at the previous sampling rates. Here, the signal sampling is performed digitally to emulate the sampling made by electronic ADCs operating at the corresponding sampling rates. After the electronic ADCs, the different signals are time-interleaved to obtain the equivalent sampling rate for the

photonic-assisted ADC, $f_{s,eq} = 5 \cdot f_s$. Figures 6(g)-(i) show the time-interleaving process, where the equivalent sampling rate of the photonic-assisted ADC, $f_{s,eq}$, is increased up to $125, 50$ and 25 GS/s, respectively for $\lambda = 1531.6, 1534$ and 1538 nm. All in all, the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC reaches a sampling rate N times higher than that of the electronic ADCs used, being N the number of samples of the TTDL. In our experiment, $N = 5$, so that we require 5 electronic ADCs with lower sampling rate to achieve a high-speed ADC by performing the optical replication and time-interleaving processes. Figure 7 illustrates the relation between the required sampling rate for the electronic ADCs (orange) and the equivalent sampling rate obtained with the proposed MCF-based ADC (blue) as a function of the operation wavelength. As a limit case, at the optical wavelength of $\lambda = 1534$ nm, the differential time delay between samples is $T_s = 20$ ps, so that, by (2), the required sampling rate for the electronic ADCs is 10 GS/s,

Fig. 6. Measured experimental results for the proposed photonic-assisted time-interleaved ADC based on a dispersion-diversity heterogeneous MCF at the optical wavelengths of (a), (d), (g) 1538 nm, (b), (e), (h) 1534 nm, and (c), (f), (i) 1531.6 nm. (a-c) Measured waveforms for cores 3 up to 7; (d-f) sampled waveforms at sampling rates $f_s = 5, 10$ and 25 GS/s, respectively; (g-i) resulting time-interleaved signals where the overall ADC sampling rate is increased up to $f_{s,eq} = 25, 50$ and 125 GS/s, respectively.

which is the current sampling rate limit for commercial electronic ADCs. At this operation wavelength, however, the equivalent sampling rate for the proposed MCF-based photonic-assisted ADC reaches 50 GS/s.

The major limitations that can affect time-interleaved ADCs are related to synchronization mismatches between the parallel channels, which could lead to severe penalties on the signal-to-noise and distortion ratios and cause a considerable reduction on the ADC effective number of bits, [12,25]. In first place, the signal amplitudes require proper management to guarantee maximum similarity between the replicas carried out by the parallel channels to minimize undesirable effects caused by these imbalances. In this regard, amplitude equalization through a set of VOAs is indispensable at the input of the electronic ADCs, as shown in Fig. 6.

In second place, random jitter is one of the main parameters that determine the performance of an ADC. Up to date, commercial ADCs can reach jitter values as low as 50 fs, with typical values ranging from 60 to 80 fs. The use of parallel channels, however, can cause clock synchronization skews that can increase the time uncertainty and thus degrade the jitter performance of the resulting ADC. Thus, as in every time-interleaved ADC, precise clock synchronization is indispensable to achieve high-speed high-performance ADCs. Another possible jitter degradation source could be caused by the temporal stability of the parallel replicas. Since the signal replicas must be adequately time synchronized at the input of the electronic ADCs, slight temporal misalignments can also introduce time uncertainty penalty and mask the low-jitter performance of the electronic ADCs involved. In this context, we have evaluated the group delay stability of the implemented TTDL. Figures 8(a)-(c) show the measured differential group delay variation between adjacent

Fig. 7. Comparison between the sampling rate required for the parallel electronic ADCs (orange) and the resulting sampling rate for the MCF-based time-interleaved photonic ADC (blue) as a function of the optical wavelength.

samples within a 2-hour time interval, respectively at the optical wavelengths of $\lambda = 1531.6$, 1534 and 1538 nm. The measurements were performed in laboratory conditions but without a specific controlled environment. The maximum temperature variation was below 1 °C during the measurement time, while the humidity was kept within a 2% range. The MCF was not isolated from other environmental effects such as vibrations.

The time delay was measured via an optical interferometric based technique by calculating the fast Fourier transform of the measured interference pattern created between two adjacent samples, [23]. The maximum differential group delay variation between adjacent samples within the 2-hour measurement time interval is kept below 150 fs, while the standard deviation is below 100 fs. As we see, these values are almost on the order of the current best-case jitter characteristics of commercial electronic ADCs, so that the possible jitter penalty increase caused by the temporal stability of the MCF is almost negligible as compared with the unique performance benefits of the proposed configuration, including the ADC equivalent sampling rate improvement, the continuous ADC sampling rate tunability or the remote system reconfigurability.

Fig. 8. Measurements of the TTDL temporal stability within a 2-hour time interval without a specific controlled environment. Variation of the differential group delay between adjacent cores as a function of time at the optical wavelength of (a) 1531.6, (b) 1534 and (c) 1538 nm.

V. CONCLUSION

We have proposed and experimentally demonstrated, for the first time to our knowledge, a new approach for photonic-assisted time-interleaved analog-to-digital conversion based on a dispersion-engineered heterogeneous MCF. The MCF is 5-km long and comprises 7 different trench-assisted cores whose refractive index profiles were properly designed to behave as a tunable sampled TTDL. We successfully demonstrated analog-to-digital conversion with continuous sampling rate tunability with the optical wavelength from 25 up to 125 GS/s by sweeping the optical wavelength of operation from $\lambda = 1538$ down to 1531.6 nm. The measured TTDL temporal stability was within a 150-fs maximum variability range, which is in the order of the current best-case jitter performance of commercial electronic ADCs. It should be noted that one of the main advantages of using a MCF to carry the parallel channels relies on the fact that all the cavities are subject to similar environmental conditions, so that the effect of random channel misalignments are more controlled than in other parallel configurations. All in all, our approach provides unique performance benefits in terms of ADC factor multiplication sampling rate as compared to commercial electronic ADCs, continuous ADC sampling rate tunability with the optical wavelength and remote system reconfigurability.

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